

Prosiding Seminar Nasional
Adiwidya 9
Pascasarjana ITB

**“SMART CITY AS AN ALTERNATIVE SOLUTION
FOR URBAN DEVELOPMENT AND EQUITY IN
INDONESIA”**

Dilakukan secara daring, 23-24 Oktober 2021

PROSIDING ADIWIDYA 9

SMART CITY AS AN ALTERNATIVE SOLUTION FOR URBAN DEVELOPMENT AND EQUITY IN INDONESIA

- ◆ *Talkshow Smart Education*
- ◆ *Talkshow Smart Social Economy*
- ◆ *Talkshow Smart Science Technology*
- ◆ *International Webinar Smart City*

ADIWIDYA 9 | #SINERGIKANPERAN
KAMIL PASCASARJANA ITB

Baros International Animation Festival as a Brand Activation Cimahi Smart City

Nada Arina Romli^{1,a),*,†} and Suci Nurpratiwi^{2,}

¹Universitas Negeri Jakarta. Fakultas Ilmu Sosial. Jalan Rawamangun Muka Jakarta.

²Universitas Negeri Jakarta. Fakultas Ilmu Sosial. Jalan Rawamangun Muka Jakarta

^{a)}nadaarina@unj.ac.id

^{b)}sucinurpratiwi@unj.ac.id

Abstract.

The purpose of this study was to find out how the implementation of the Baros International Animation Festival activities as a branding activity for the city of Cimahi as a smart city. This research uses qualitative research with constructivist paradigm and case study approach. The research subjects in this study were representatives of the Cimahi city government, representatives and administrators of the Cimahi Creative City Forum who were actively involved in the development of the animation industry in the city of Cimahi. The method of data collection in this research used semi-structured in-depth interviews, passive participant observation, and literature study. The type of sampling used in this research is snowball sampling. Meanwhile, the theories used in the analysis are stakeholder theory and symbolic interaction theory. The results of this study are the reason for holding the Baros International Animation Festival is an effort to strengthen Cimahi as a smart city and a center for the development of the national animation industry where CCA is a development partner for the telematics industry in the city of Cimahi. BIAF is understood by the city of Cimahi as a city promotion event, an event to actualize Cimahi as a creative city and a smart city. There are 3 activities in BIAF, namely business meeting, masterclass, talkshow, exhibition and competition. The Cimahi City Government delegates to CCA to organize BIAF every year. The conclusion in this study is that BIAF is present on the awareness of the Cimahi City Government in partnership with CCA in taking the opportunity as the only city in Indonesia that develops industry telematics-based creative, the Cimahi City Government and CCA have an almost uniform understanding. Regarding BIAF as a promotional activity for the animation industry in Indonesia, the BIAF implementation process goes through the following stages: situation analysis, planning and programming, action and communication, and evaluation, are still not optimal carried out due to the lack of supporting resources..

Keywords: Baros, International, Animation, Cimahi, Smart, City

1. Background

The creative animation industry has the potential to develop in Indonesia. With more than 250 million people, 30% of whom are upper middle class, Indonesia is a huge market for the entertainment and media industries. Indonesia is also believed to have capital resources or human resources that deserve to be aligned with other countries. This is evident from the many Indonesian animators who are worldwide, such as Roni Gani who became the animator of the famous Transformer and Pacific Rim films, Rini Sugianto, Andre Surya, etc. In addition, Indonesia's rich culture makes it an unlimited source of ideas in the creative process. The things mentioned above are opportunities that Indonesia

has if it wants to compete with other countries in the world. But unfortunately, the animation market in Indonesia is still dominated by foreigners and weak in terms of publicity. The lack of appreciation and business knowledge of animation industry players in Indonesia has caused many animation businesses to collapse.

Baros International Animation Festival is a special international event organized by the City of Cimahi in collaboration with the Cimahi Creative Association. This event took place on 27-30 November 2015 attracting thousands of people from all over Indonesia and even abroad to attend this grand event. There were 30 speakers present to fill this event. Speakers are not only from Indonesia. But also from 8 countries, namely Malaysia, the Philippines, New Zealand, France, Iran, Germany and Thailand.

The implementation of BIAF aims to promote the animation industry in Indonesia, both domestic and foreign stakeholders. With the holding of BIAF, it opens fresh air for animation industry owners in Indonesia and animation businesses abroad. Thus encouraging a business agreement in the field of animation in the context of developing the animation industry in Indonesia. In 2014, was the second event of BIAF where in 2013 was the first BIAF event. In 2014, BIAF took the theme "Hidden Talents Global Exposure" which describes the promising animation industry in Indonesia. There are 5 agendas in BIAF activities including masterclass, talk show, exhibition, business meeting, and competition. One of the agendas in BIAF is to introduce the city of Cimahi as a driving force for the national animation industry. With the promotion of Cimahi as a national animation development city, it is hoped that more Indonesian animators and from all over the world will come to Cimahi. In addition, according to the Mayor of Cimahi, Atty Suharty, the implementation of BIAF 2014 is to confirm Cimahi as a digital smart city, because it prioritizes the national animation industry, so that more investors will invest in Cimahi City and increase the Cimahi city budget. animation which was later designated as the center of national animation development in the Master Plan for the Acceleration and Expansion of Indonesian Economic Development (MP3EI) 2011-2025. This is also stated in the Road Map for the Development of Cimahi City Industrial Core Competencies for 2012-2016 which was made by the Cimahi City Government which was later stipulated in the Regulation of the Minister of Industry of the Republic of Indonesia Number 137 of 20112 which stated that the core industry of Cimahi City was the telematics industry which focus on the animation industry. So that the existence of BIAF can bring the name of the City of Cimahi to be increasingly known by the Indonesian people through marketing the results of the animation industry and elevating the branding of the City of Cimahi as a Creative City. BIAF is one of the successes of the City of Cimahi Government in organizing an event.

This study aims to see how the implementation of BIAF as an activity to strengthen the city of Cimahi as a smart city. This is because of the stereotype that was built in Cimahi City as a military city because of the many TNI facilities that were built in Cimahi City. In addition, the Cimahi City Government and CCA must be faced with stereotypes about Cimahi City which is a small city in West Java which is still underestimated by stakeholders and stereotypes about Indonesia whose animation industry has not been taken into account in the international world. CCA is still finding it difficult to gain trust and invite stakeholders to participate in supporting BIAF implementation. The stakeholders in question are stakeholders from within the country and abroad, consisting of business people, such as producers, investors, or potential buyers, animation actors, especially from Indonesia as potential sellers, government, media, animation enthusiasts, and the general public. This causes BIAF to have no concrete impact after its implementation, namely the occurrence of business transactions on a large scale which is the main goal that CCA wants to encourage through this event.

2. Literature

2.1. George Herbert Mead's Symbolic Interaction Theory

The perspective of symbolic interaction is actually under the umbrella of a larger perspective which is often called a phenomenological perspective or an interpretive perspective. (Mulyana, 2010: 59). In

this perspective, the names of George Herbert Mead (1863-1931), Charles Horton Cooley (1846-1929), focused on the interaction between individuals and groups. They found that these individuals interacted by using symbols, which contained signs, cues and words. After this figure, then the steps were continued by the sociologists of symbolic interactionism Herbert Blumer (1962) and Erving Goffman (1959). (Riyadi Soeprapto, 2002:69)

Symbolic interactionism evolved from a concern to language; but Mead developed it in a different and quite unique direction. Mead claims that language allows us to become beings aware of our individuality, and a key element in this process of symbols. (Riyadi Soeprapto, 2002:70)

In research on BIAF 2014 as an activity that reflects the branding of Cimahi city as a smart city, the researcher uses the Symbolic Interaction theory from George Herbert Mead. Communication activities cannot be separated from the role of symbols or symbols. Especially in written verbal communication, where every message conveyed is in the form of writing and symbols. The writings and symbols have a responsibility to be a bridge for interaction between the communicator and the communicant.

Likewise with the campaign. In its implementation, the campaign conveys its message using symbols or symbols, either in the form of writing or pictures that can strengthen information about Cimahi as a smart city.

Symbolic interaction is an activity that is characteristic of humans, namely communication or the exchange of symbols that are given meaning. Symbolic interaction assumes that humans can understand things from experience. A person's perception is always translated in symbols. A meaning is learned through interactions among people, and that meaning arises because of the exchange of symbols in social groups. On the other hand, symbolic interaction views that all social structures and institutions and social institutions are created by interactions between people. In addition, a person's behavior is not absolutely determined by events in the past, but is also done intentionally.

Mead developed the theory of symbolic interactionism in the 1920s when he was professor of philosophy at the University of Chicago. However, his ideas on symbolic interactionism developed rapidly after his students published their notes and lectures, especially through books that became the main reference for the theory of symbolic interactionism, namely *Mind, self and society* (Mulyana, 2010: 68).

Mead's most famous work outlines three critical concepts needed to structure a discussion of symbolic interactionism theory. These three concepts influence each other in terms of symbolic interactionism. From that, the human mind (mind) and social interactions (self/self with others) are used to interpret and mediate the society (society) in which we live. Meaning comes from interaction and not in any other way. At the same time "mind" and "self" arise in the social context of society. The reciprocal influence between society, individual experience and interaction becomes the material for study in the symbolic interactionism tradition (Elvinaro, 2007: 136).

3. Method

This study uses qualitative research methods because it tries to observe the program and the people who in this study are the parties involved in BIAF activities as a branding activity for Cimahi city as a smart city which observes interactions and language. From the results of these interactions, the people in the BIAF event tried to construct the meaning of the new branding of the city of Cimahi from the city of Military Cimahi to a smart city. This research produces descriptive data in the form of written or spoken words from written or spoken words from the parties involved and their observed behavior, which means that these data are based on the point of view of the subject being studied (emic).) plus the analysis based on the researcher (etic). This is in accordance with Creswell's view that qualitative research is methods to explore and understand the meaning that a number of individuals or groups or people ascribe to social or humanitarian problems. This qualitative research process involves important efforts, such as asking questions and procedures, collecting specific data from participants, analyzing data inductively from specific themes to general themes, and interpreting the meaning of the data. The final report for this research has a flexible structure or framework. Anyone involved in this form of research must apply a research perspective that is inductive style, focuses on individual

meaning, and translates the complexity of a person (adapted from Creswell, 2007 in Creswell, 2012: 4-5)

So in qualitative research, a researcher enters the natural order of the people he studies. Researchers in qualitative research go into the field themselves to collect data. The data obtained in the form of qualitative data, not quantitative because the data obtained does not require measurement. Therefore, in qualitative research there is no absolute truth. "Qualitative researchers are not looking for absolute truth." (Nasution, 2002: 6)

While the study approach in this study uses a case study because where the researcher explores a certain phenomenon (case) in a time and activity (program, event, process, institution or social group) and collects detailed and in-depth information using various data collection procedures during certain period. Stake (1995) provides the view that case studies are

A research strategy in which the researcher carefully investigates a program, event, activity, process, or group of individuals. Cases are limited by time and activity, and the researcher collects complete information using various data collection procedures based on the allotted time. (Creswell, 2012: 20).

While John W. Creswell revealed (1998: 61), that :

"A case study is an exploration of a "bounded system" or a case (multiple cases) over time through detailed, in-depth data collection involving multiple sources of information rich in context"

Based on the explanation of the case study definition above, Creswell suggests several characteristics of a case study, namely: (1) identifying the "case" for a study; (2) The case is a "system bound" by time and place; (3) Case studies use various sources of information in collecting data to provide a detailed and in-depth description of the response to an event and (4) Using a case study approach, researchers will "spend time" in describing the context or setting for a case.

Based on the explanation above, it can be stated that a case study is an exploration of "a bound system" or "a case or various cases" which from time to time goes through in-depth data collection and involves various sources of "rich" information in a context. . This bound system is bound by time and place while cases can be studied from a program, event, activity or an individual

4. Result and Discussion

Special activities or special events, such as the Baros International Animation Festival, are tools of promotion for a company or organization to attract the attention of the press and the public to certain companies or products displayed in the event through the public relations function. Yeverbaum (in Pudjiastuti 2010: xvii) suggests that:

"Special events are effective vehicles publicity they help market your company, product, or service to the public, and they are promotable and can get you a lot of press coverage"

Promotion and public relations have a very close relationship as stated by Kotler who sees public relations as a mass promotion tool where public relations serves to foster good relations with various communities around the company by getting favorable publicity, fostering a good corporate image, and handling or suppress rumors, stories, and adverse events (Kotler, 2011: 181).

The ability of special events to promote a product or brand will ultimately have an impact on marketing. Public Relations is currently also associated with marketing objectives, namely to encourage purchases. This is related to the purpose of holding BIAF, one of which is to obtain business transactions in the Indonesian animation industry. When stakeholders find out about the results of the animation industry by Indonesian creators through BIAF, they then have confidence in this animation industry, which is expected to attract stakeholders, especially animation businesses at home and abroad, to buy animated products that are promoted or to help invest in the development of animation products. the. The two principles, public relations and marketing, complement each other.

The merging of the two became known as Marketing Public Relations. MPR is the process of planning, implementing, and evaluating programs that encourage purchase and customer satisfaction through communication containing reliable information and impressions that describe the company and its products in accordance with customer needs, wants, and interests (Harris, 1991: 12). . MPR supports the marketing mix, especially the promotion mix, which has the power to persuade and educate the public or the public at the same time.

The implementation of BIAF 2014 is divided into three phases, namely planning, implementation and evaluation in line with the concept of management processes in public relations activities according to Scott M. Cutlip and Allen H. Centre, (2005) there are phases of planning and making decisions (planning-decision), communicating and implementation (communicating-action), evaluate (evaluation).

1. Planning and DecisionStage

The BIAF planning phase is in line with the planning-decision concept. At this stage, attitudes, opinions, ideas and reactions related to policies and the determination of organizational work programs that are in line with the interests or desires of interested parties begin to be given: Here's what we can do? (what we can do)

Steps in planning activities:

- 1.Introduction to the situation
2. Goal setting
- 3.Definition of audience
4. Media selection and PR techniques
5. Budget planning
6. Measurement of results (Jefkins, 2003: 57).

In line with the planning concept expressed by Gregory, in the BIAF planning stage, messages and strategies are prepared. The campaign message is a means that will bring the target to follow what is desired from the campaign program which will ultimately be conveyed to the achievement of campaign goals.

The Cimahi City Government and CCA use informal methods, namely in the form of FGDs or discussion forums conducted by CCA with the Cimahi City Government, as well as focus groups that are often conducted by CCA with several animation actors in Cimahi City. In this forum, each person provides opinions or input for BIAF so that it becomes one of the references for the implementing team in BIAF to carry out their program. The opinions expressed in this forum are opinions that come from subjective perspectives and their respective interpretations so that they do not necessarily represent the opinions of other stakeholders. Therefore, according to Cutlip, Center, and Broom, findings in focus groups or community forums are only a basis for further study in formal surveys and obtaining scientific data (2005: 337). However, CCA did not continue this research into more formal research, but went straight to the planning stage.

2. Action and Communicating Stage

The execution stage in the management process of public relations activities is included in the action stage (implementation). This action stage determines what PR tactics will be used to execute this campaign. Tactics very much depend on the goals and objectives that the campaign program will target. The choice of tactics is actually only based on two functions, namely linking and convincing functions. First, the tactics of identifying and linking campaign programs with targets through certain communication media. Furthermore, the tactics to convince the target think, believe, act in accordance with the objectives of the campaign program. (Venus, 2004: 153)

The Event and Promotion Division within CCA is the division responsible for the event organizer for activities related to promotion. BIAF is the biggest event held by the City of Cimahi, so this event requires large resources

Therefore, the implementation involves all CCA members who are divided into several divisions. The implementation is also assisted by volunteers who are students who are carrying out internships at CCA and from the results of recruitment.

Communicating this event to the target public is done through various channels, namely media, relationship utilization, roadshow, and email. The use of media at BIAF consists of 3 types, namely online media, external media space, and mass media:

The online media in question is the use of websites (<http://biaf.co.id>), twitter (@barosanimafest), facebook (Barosanimafest), and community portals in the field of animation.

Outdoor media, such as banners, billboards, posters, and banners.

Mass media, print and electronic. In BIAF 2014, CCA collaborated with 2 media, namely 99ers and Kompas.

From the use of all these communication channels, online media, the use of relationships, and e-mail are the most frequently used by CCA members in the implementation of BIAF. The use of online media is considered as an effective medium to touch many people and does not cost a lot. Communication media via email is considered to be an effective medium for CCA to invite animation actors from various countries, business people, producers, especially to approach potential speakers.

Furthermore, so that BIAF's goals can be achieved as planned, and the needs of stakeholders can be channeled, CCA members implement it into 5 BIAF activities, namely business meetings, masterclasses, talk shows, exhibitions, and competitions. Other activities include a welcome dinner and screening of animated films. Through these activities, the goal of promoting the Indonesian animation industry, conducting networking, cooperation, and even animation business transactions, as well as being a source of knowledge in the field of animation can be achieved.

3. Evaluasi Stage

Evaluation is the last component of a series of event management processes. Although it ranks last, its benefits and importance are no different from the planning and implementation stages of the campaign. Campaign evaluation is defined as a systematic effort to assess various aspects related to the process of implementing and achieving campaign objectives. From this definition, it can be seen that the evaluation is not only carried out at the end of the campaign, but also when the campaign is in progress. The definition also shows that there are two main aspects that need to be considered in conducting an evaluation, namely how the campaign was implemented and what results were achieved as a consequence of implementing the program.

Regarding what and what level of evaluation should be carried out, Ostegaard (2002) says it depends on the purpose of the evaluation itself. In general, according to Ostegaard, campaign evaluation can be categorized into four levels as follows: campaign level, attitude level, behavior level, and problem level. Evaluation of activities or BIAF is carried out after activities or work programs and targets the attitude level and problem level.

1. Attitude level

At the level of attitude evaluation can be done using a survey method or a simple test (simple test). Survey methods are used for large samples, while simple tests are generally used for a limited target group, which are also very popular for measuring the knowledge or skills a person has acquired as a result of organizing a campaign.

In Ostegaard's perspective, there are four aspects related to evaluation at the attitude level, namely cognitive aspects (knowledge, awareness, trust, etc.), affective (liking, sympathy, appreciation, support, etc.), conative (commitment to action), and skills aspects. or skills. At this evaluation level, campaign implementers also construct the same questions before and after the campaign. To find out the difference, we just need to subtract the score after the campaign from the pre-campaign.

Evaluation of activities or work programs in BIAF at the level to measure attitudes the instrument used is a questionnaire, but it is carried out only after the campaign by constructing questions whether their knowledge increases, their awareness increases about the topic in the activity, whether they like the activity or work program and if the evaluation of skills is seen from, for example, if the activity is about internet marketing, how many use internet tools in marketing are asked after 1 month of

campaign implementation. The implementer also constructs questions regarding the need for future activities that are still related to the activities that have been carried out as a form of proposed activities from participants. This evaluation question is constructed based on targets or indicators that have been set by the implementers of activities or work programs, in this case the City Government, related agencies and the community. After the survey is carried out using a questionnaire, the evaluation is included in the performance appraisal form based on the standards from the Minister of Home Affairs to measure the outputs and outcomes of the activities or work programs.

2. Problem level

At this level the evaluation can be done easily or otherwise it is very difficult and takes a long time. Problem or problem here is defined as the gap between reality and expectations or what should happen. Evaluation of the level of problems carried out in BIAF 2014 activities or work programs is carried out by verbal evaluation in the form of a forum or meeting called Money (monitoring and evaluation) by inviting SOPD or community members who carry out activities regarding whether the targets or indicators set have been achieved based on the output and outcomes that have been calculated in the attitude evaluation. Then the results of this evaluation are proposed activities that are still related to past activities and improve results that have not been achieved in previous activities.

The 2014 BIAF event supporting Cimahi as a Smart City can be explained through Mead's symbolic interaction theory, the construction of the 2014 BIAF event as a smart city branding is obtained through a process of internal interaction (self) then mediated through what Mead calls society (society) which means an endless social process that precedes thought and self. Society has an important role in shaping the mind and self. At a more specific societal level, defining institutions as "common responses in the community" or "customs of community life". In this stage, the construction of a new city brand is mutually agreed upon within the scope of the Cimahi City community.

Mead's book *Mind, Self and Society*, "Mead's preference may not be mind and then society; but it is society first and then the thoughts that arise in society..." (quoted Miller, 1982a: 2). This inverse of the title by Faris reflects the extent of the fact that Mead himself admits that, society, or more broadly, social life, is in accordance with the priorities in Mead's analysis. Mead describes his concern in terms of language:

"According to social psychology, we do not construct group behavior in terms of the behavior of each individual who forms it; we start from the social whole from the activities of certain complex groups, and where we analyze the behavior of the individuals who make it up... That is, we seek to explain the behavior of social groups rather than explain the organized behavior of social groups in terms of the behavior of the individuals who make them up. . According to social psychology, the whole of society is before the parts (individuals), not that the parts are before the whole; and the part is explained from the point of view of the whole, not the whole which is explained from the point of view of the parts. (Ritzer and Goodman, 2004: 271-272)

According to Mead, the social whole precedes individual thought both logically and temporarily. Individuals who think and are self-aware are logically impossible according to Mead's theory without being preceded by the existence of social groups to produce the development of a mental state of self-awareness.

Mead's book, *Mind Self and Society* can be explained that the cyclicity in the theory of symbolic interaction can be inverse or reversed, such as meaning construction is obtained by the sources from the results of mutual agreement or in the language that Mead utters "a shared response in the community" which is none other than the related informants. with the Branding of Cimahi City as a Smart City which then occurs an interaction, in Mead's terms is Self which is basically the ability to accept oneself as an object. The self is the special ability to be both subject and object. The self presupposes a social process: interpersonal communication.

References

- [1] Ardianto, Elvinaro.(2007). Filsafat Ilmu Komunikasi. Bandung: Remaja Rosdakarya
- [2] Center and Broom, Cutlip. (2005). Effective Public Relations (Edisi kedelapan). Jakarta: PT. Indeks Kelompok Gramedia
- [3] Creswel, John.W. (1998). Qualitative Inquiry And Research Design. London. Sage Publications, Inc
- [4] Creswel, John.W. (2012). Research Design: Pendekatan Kualitatif, Kuantitatif dan Mixed. Yogyakarta: Pustaka Pelajar
- [5] Cimahi Creative Association. (2014). Annual Report CCA 2014. Cimahi: Cimahi Creative Association
- [6] Deddy, Mulyana. (2010). Metodologi Penelitian Kualitatif. Bandung: PT. Remaja. Rosdakarya
- [7] Harris, T. L. (1991). The Marketers Guide to Public Relations. Canada: John Wiley & Sons, Inc
- [8] Jefkins, Frank. (2003). *Public Relations* Edisi 5. Jakarta : Erlangga
- [9] Kotler, Philip & Gary Amstrong. (2011). Principle Of Marketing. New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
- [10] Nasution, S. (2002). Metode Penelitian Naturalistik Kualitatif. Bandung: Tarsito
- [11] Ritzer, George dan Goodman Douglas. (2004). Teori Sosiologi Modern. Jakarta : Prenada Media
- [12] Soeprapto, Riyadi. (2002). Interaksionisme Simbolik. Malang: Averroes Press
- [13] Venus, Antar. (2004). Manajemen Kampanye: Panduan Teoritis dan Praktis dalam Mengefektifkan Kampanye Komunikasi. Bandung: Rekatama Simbiosis
- [14] <http://www.cimahikota.go.id/news/detail/1256> Accessed on 5 Oktober 2021
- [15] Permenperind Nomor 137 Tahun 2011. Diakses melalui http://regulasi.kemenperin.go.id/site/baca_peraturan/1200 pAccessed on

ADIWIDYA 9

KAMIL PASCASARJANA ITB

Follow kanal informasi Adiwidya 9:

Instagram : **@adiwidya**itb****

Website : <http://kamilpasca.itb.ac.id/adiwidya-9/>

Prosiding Seminar Nasional
Adiwidya 9
Pascasarjana ITB

Alamat Redaksi

Keluarga Mahasiswa Islam (KAMIL) Pascasarjana ITB,
Gedung Kayu Lt. 2, Kompleks Masjid Salman ITB,
Jl. Ganesha No. 10, Bandung,
40132 <https://kamilpasca.itb.ac.id/>

9 772746 488075